

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF BERYLLIUM WITH 5-NITROSALICYLIC ACID

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Measurements of pH and conductance with 5-nitrosalicylic acid show that unlike salicylic acid, which forms two complexes with beryllium, nitrosalicylic acid forms only a rather unstable 1:1 complex. The results show that the presence of a nitro group affects the chelate-forming nature to a marked extent.

Beryllium complexes with salicylate ions were studied by Rosenheim and Lehmann (*Annalen*, 1924, 440, 153), Varma and Mehrotra (this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 381), and also by Singh and Prakash (*ibid.*, 1957, 34, 197). The present work has been undertaken with a view to studying the complex compounds of nitrosalicylic acid with beryllium and to ascertaining the effect of nitro group on chelation of the ions.

EXPERIMENTAL

N/10 Beryllium nitrate (B.D.H.-A.R.) and a standard *N*/2 potassium nitrosalicylate solution were used for the experiments. Be in the former was determined as oxide (Vogel, "Inorganic Analysis", 1948, p. 536). Conductance was determined with Callen Kamp's Kohlrausch slide wire having an audiofrequency oscillator with circuit and a headphone for detecting null point. Measurements of pH were determined with a Beckman glass electrode pH meter (H_2PH). Results are shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

DISCUSSION

Curves K₁-K₄ of Fig. 1 show the effect of dropwise addition of *M*/2-KOH on mixtures of beryllium nitrate containing 0, 1, 2, 3 moles respectively of potassium salt of 5-nitrosalicylic

acid. A blank experiment with potassium nitrosalicylate alone increased the pH of the solution to 9, indicating the non-appearance of hydroxyl hydrogen of potassium nitrosalicylate by the addition of alkali.

Curve K_1 for the blank shows a sudden change in pH when two moles of the alkali are added, indicating complete formation of beryllium hydroxide.

Curve K_2 with beryllium nitrate and one mole of potassium nitrosalicylate shows an inflection on the addition of one equivalent of alkali, inflection occurring at pH 4 (~), thus indicating formation of a complex containing beryllium and nitrosalicylate in the ratio 1 : 1. The probable reaction on the addition of alkali (Varma and Mehrotra, *loc. cit.*) on the reaction mixture may be represented as :

Curves K_3 and K_4 , where beryllium contains 2 and 3 moles respectively of the nitrosalicylate, also show only one inflection at pH 4.1, indicating that only one complex is formed in the ratio 1 : 1.

To confirm the above results, the experiments were repeated by measurements of conductance. Fig. 2 (curves K_5 - K_8) shows the conductometric titrations of beryllium nitrate and potassium nitrosalicylate in the ratios 1 : 0, 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 respectively against standard NH_4OH . Curve K_5 (blank) shows only a slight increase in conductance by the addition of NH_4OH . The reaction can be represented as :

Curve K_6 , where one mole of nitrosalicylate is present, shows that the graph is almost horizontal after the addition of one mole of alkali, indicating, as in the case of pH measurements, that some of the beryllium ions have been used up in complex formation. The rise in conductance by the addition of alkali is greater than that in curve K_5 as in this case the complex Be ions are replaced by smaller ammonium ions. The conductance of complex Be ions is less than that of ordinary Be ions (Varma and Mehrotra, *loc. cit.*).

Curves K_7 and K_8 , where two and three moles of nitrosalicylate are added, also are in accordance with the above results. The absence of a higher complex obtained in case of salicylic acid indicates that nitro group hinders chelation.